

Decarbonising energy-intensive industries with plasma-assisted combustion

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1. INTRODUCTION

For almost 100 years, the glass production process has improved by rebuilding or adapting different innovative low-carbon technologies that are much more energy-efficient: waste heat recovery technologies, ORC cycles, new insulation material usage, energy management, automation systems, and other innovative symbiotic technologies. Energy efficiency improvements directly reduce CO₂ emissions: specific energy consumption and energy-related CO₂ emissions have been reduced by more than 75% over the past century. However, these improvements have almost reached their thermodynamic limit; significant reductions of CO₂ emissions are no longer possible with current techniques and the combustion of natural gas or other fossil fuels. What is needed is an energy transition and even greater circularity in glass production in the areas where the potential exists.

“Flexible Hybrid Furnace of the Future” is the vision of the European glass industry to meet the European Green Deal objective of cutting Europe’s carbon emissions and contributing to EU climate neutrality. New approaches and technologies should be developed to decarbonise the entire glass sector as effectively as fast as possible, and green alternatives to natural gas for alternative carbon-neutral fuels must be found.

This work presents the first results of the Horizon Europe project GIFFT, with the overall objective to develop a sustainable, hybrid, and biofuel flexible heat production technology and process that can be integrated into industrial glass manufacturing through efficient plasma-assisted combustion and gasification systems.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The concept of GIFFT is to develop and validate a flexible hybrid furnace operation for optimal use of freely available low-cost green electricity and low-carbon biofuels to facilitate the transition from natural gas towards a new low-carbon and more dynamic heat production. The GIFFT process can propose high fuel flexibility and more dynamic operation regarding energy and fuel market changes by combining plasma-assisted biomass gasification and hybrid fuel flexible combustion. The process is designed to enable continuous operation of the glass-making plant units throughout the year with many operating hours. The hybrid operational and fuel flexibility is analysed using standard flow sheets to calculate energy and mass balances by changing between four main modes: Base Case, Biomass Case, Green Electricity Case, and Green Hydrogen Case. The hybrid operational and fuel flexibility is analysed using standard flow sheets to calculate energy and mass balances by changing between four main modes: Base Case, Biomass Case, Green Electricity Case and Green Hydrogen Case.

The first combustion tests were also carried out to visually assess the flame geometry for adaptation to existing incinerators. This test compared the flames of different fuel-oxygen compositions produced by conventional and plasma-assisted combustors. In the case of conventional combustion, the flame was generated using non-premixed combustion of natural gas (CH₄ ~96vol.%) and oxygen or hydrogen and oxygen. The thermal capacity of the burner was about 80 kW. In the case of the plasma-assisted burner prototype, the flame was generated from the same mixtures while maintaining a thermal capacity of up to 50% of the total energy released as electricity.

3. RESULTS

The concept of GIFFT is to develop and validate a flexible hybrid furnace operation for optimal use of freely available low-cost green electricity and low-carbon biofuels to facilitate the transition from natural gas towards a new low-carbon and more dynamic heat production. By combining plasma-assisted combustion, the GIFFT process can propose high fuel flexibility and more dynamic operation regarding energy and fuel market changes.

The burner is composed of a plasma torch generator in the core, which is surrounded by additional rings for different gaseous fuels and oxidizer supplies. Typically, the thermal plasma is operated as a pilot burner, allowing it to smoothly switch between different selected gases and stabilize the flame in case of fuel composition changes. This enables reliably operating a glass-making process that is very sensitive to temperature variation. Meanwhile, when green electricity at low-price is available on the market, green electricity at a low price is available on the market, and hydrogen or another cheap gas combustion is boosted with thermal energy provided by a plasma torch. This reduces fuel consumption and converts the excess electricity into a sensitive heating process.

Figure 1 presents the latest flame geometry test visualisation results, which allowed us to understand the operational specifics of plasma-assisted combustion of both methane, in the form of natural gas, and hydrogen.

Figure 1: Plasma-assisted generated flame by combusting hydrogen (a) and natural gas (b) in oxygen.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Initial investigations have allowed us to identify the optimum gas feed points for the prototype burner to achieve flexibility and a wide range of operating parameters. In the next stages, the plasma-assisted burner will be further developed to assess not only the geometrical characteristics of the flame but also other key parameters such as flame spectral emissions, heat radiation intensity, pollutant emissions, etc.

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